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COLORING OF SPEECH LABELS IN THE LANGUAGE OF IMAGES

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КОЛОРИТ РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В ЯЗЫКЕ ОБРАЗОВ

Abstract.

Speech etiquette mainly include winged-idiomatic expressions, proverbs, phraseological units, wise folk sayings, archaic beliefs such as applause, cursing, as well as locally figurative expressions. These phrases, ready-made speech models, developed in accordance with the national thinking, ethnography and traditions of our people, satisfy people in all cases, create a pleasant atmosphere in them, guide the interviewer's activities and ensure mutual understanding. Movlud Suleymanli and Ilyas Afandiyev appeal to the images of their artistic heritage mainly to strengthen the ideas and opinions they put forward, to present their thoughts more coherently, to convey the point fully and most importantly, to state their position with reference to generalizing wise sayings born from the experience of the great people.

Аннотация.

Речевой этикет в основном включают в себя крылато-идиоматические выражения, пословицы, фразеологизмы, мудрые народные поговорки, архаические поверья типа аплодисментов, ругательств, а также локально образные выражения. Эти фразы, готовые речевые модели, разработанные в соответствии с национальным мышлением, этнографией и традициями нашего народа, во всех случаях удовлетворяют людей, создают в них приятную атмосферу, направляют деятельность интервьюера, обеспечивают взаимопонимание. Мовлуд Сулейманлы и Ильяс Афандиев обращаются к образам своего художественного наследия главным образом для усиления выдвигаемых ими идей и соображений, для более связного изложения своих мыслей, для полной передачи сути, а главное, они призывают выразить свою позицию, ссылаясь на обобщающие мудрые изречения, рожденные из большого национального опыта.

Keywords: speech etiquette, character, style, folklore, national thought

Ключевые слова: речевой этикет, образ, стиль, фольклор, национальное мышление

One of the main directions, which is widely and peculiar in fiction, includes colorful expressions reflecting the style of folk speech is the language of images, or rather speech labels with a folkloric essence, which is observed in their language. Speech labels mainly include winged-idiomatic expressions, proverbs and sayings, phraseological units, wise folk sayings, archaic beliefs such as oaths, applause, curses, as well as figurative idioms bearing local-local pronouncements. Speech labels, which give the language of images naturalness, liveliness, dynamism and playfulness, represent and present their spiritual world, psychological atmosphere, manner of communication, speech-dialect coloring arising from the tradition of historical ethnographic culture belonging to the territory to which they belong and fill their mental-psychological spirit, moral portrait and at the same time, it also enriches the linguistic-stylistic flow of the work with its unique qualities.

Starting from the epics and passing a long way, the speech labels in the language of the images created in the fiction literature with their national spirit and spiritual richness are the most beautiful quality that represents our national-spiritual values. The label given in the language of artistic images is the label of society. Each of the characters such as khan, bey and shepherd

described in the epic "Dede Gorgud" has their own speech etiquette. Gazan is a nobleman, but Garachig is a shepherd. According to the difference in status between them, Gazan Khan can express his curse so: "Let your mouth dry, Shepherd! Let your tongue rot, Shepherd, Almighty write down your forehead, Shepherd! But Shepherd Garachig has no right to go and get the house in Ghazan Khan's presence. Because the Great Oghuz noblemen would say to Gazan "He wouldn't win the infidel if he had not gone with the shepherd" (1, p.46). The words "Strike your sword, my lord Gazan, I have reached" told by the brave men who came to help Gazan enter the enemy place after him, it is the approval of the label not to break the ban. Such labels are also found in different parts of the epic.

If we look at the history of medieval literature, we'll see that speech etiquette had a special character here as well. Writing in simple language, using ordinary spoken words and talking about everyday life issues in literary works were incompatible with the high attitude to the word art of that time. Such an attitude to literature and art, along with the content of the work, meant that each word was chosen precisely on the basis of the traditional rules of poetics and the image was used in the language. Normative laws requiring the highest form perfection in medieval poetry led to the

emergence of a special poetic language of romantic, high character in the poetry of that period. Only in the 19th century after the formation of artistic prose as a special genre and the strengthening of realistic poetry, it became clear that it was not at all mandatory to use a "special" style of speech for poetic purposes, it is also possible to create works of high art using other types of styles and lexical layers of the wide nationwide language. The difference between the types of speech labels of the artistic language, which are considered to be specific styles of the literary language, lies primarily in the fact that they are processed and polished from the point of view of mastery, subordinated to the specific goals of the writer and manifested as a product of activity. A creative attitude to language can manifest itself not only in artistic language, but also in other types of speech. However, speech activity, speech etiquette become a decisive factor only in the artistic language.

In the second half of the twentieth century oral folk literature, Dede Gorgud's spirit and the poetic enthusiasm of Dede Gorgud were gaining momentum. This is also observed in Movlud Suleymanli's activity.

As a writer close to the people's spirit, he seems to be the bearer of the poetic spirit and enthusiasm of Dede Gorgud, who manifested himself vividly in the novel "Migration". In the novel "Migration" the writer gave the fate of the people within the framework of the image of a tribe. In the novel the artistic image is expressed at the level of the artistic model of the history of the people. It is possible to find a wide range of folk sayings that are manifested in the speech of images.

Doctor of Philological Sciences Mukhtar Imanov notes that the author considers the archaic perceptions specially among the people about the devil and the expressions such as "Devil entered my heart", "Devil led me astray", "Curse the devil, it can enter whoever he/she wants" transforms the form of worldview that lives in expressions into the form of artistic reflection" (2, p. 96).

In the works of the writer applause and cursing are enough, where they are considered necessary, they are brought to the speech of the image at the appropriate moment of the epic text. One of the images Gizbes: "Vomit blood, the nobleman's son! May it be water under your legs, may it not be green!.. Always wear black or dark blue dresses. Let my curse hold you and let the ground not to accept you as your grandfather Dursun!" (3, 171). Although these sayings given in the character's speech have folklore particles with a unique mythological-semantic content, the writer focuses on the causes of the misfortune that befell the old woman Gizbes, such as curses and damnations and achieves the necessary artistic-aesthetic effect.

These expressions, ready-made speech models, developed in accordance with the national thinking, ethnography and traditions of our people, satisfy people in all cases, create a good mood in them, direct the activities of the interviewer and ensure mutual understanding. Our language is rich in such expressions. In the daily speech activity of people colorful phrases are often used, which are due to their worldview, degree of literacy, intelligence and conscious attitude to lan-

guage. The appeal labels among the members of the society of each nation are part of the overall culture of that nation. Speech labels given in the language of images in fiction are the clear indicator of folk, to which the people belong.

In these profound examples of epic folklore the characters of Mavlud Suleymanli are mainly used to strengthen the ideas and opinions they put forward and present their thoughts more coherently, to exert the strong moral and psychological influence on the other side, to convey the point fully and most importantly, to generalize their position to wise sayings appeared from great folk experience they apply for the purpose of reporting. In the story "Grass" Ahmed complains about his son's lack of understanding and says to his wife, who is crying over the state of her child: "Why do you cry again? The children you gave birth look like to you... Oh, don't die my donkey, spring will come and the grass will grow..." (4, 87). The father's expression of his hopeless complaint with the proverb "Don't die my donkey, spring will come and the grass will grow" provided the more complete and lively delivery of the intended purpose. Again in the same story when Ahmad sees that his countryman Hadi wanted to hide the real reality under various pretexts to deceive him: "- Don't lose track, don't get confused, if you're a fox, I'm your tail. I saw with my eyes, he was falling from the second floor" (4, 91). The figurative meaning of the proverb "If you are a fox, I am your tail" is used here as a folk saying figuratively expressing its conclusion with reference to a phraseological pattern in the saying "I know more than you".

If you pay attention, you can clearly see that the phraseological and lexical composition of the applause and prayers in grandmother Huru's speech is based on the folklore memory of the language with all its power and energy. In every sentence, in every layer of the reminder and blessing she gave to her children the summarizing conclusions of the ethnic life experience from the depth of centuries have been considered. In addition to applause and prayers, when it is considered necessary, the writer brings its opposite position - curses and prayers - into the speech of the image at the appropriate moment of the epic text. Movlud Suleymanli shows the poetic folklore examples mainly from the language of the images he creates in his prose works. Here the age level, worldview, moral and spiritual indicators of the characters are also reflected in the characteristics of the poetic folklore sample. For example, the folkloric text told by a young mother caressing her child revives the sublimity of mother's love with memorable folklore colors and ethnographic realities: "The young mother cherishing her baby began to tell:

- Oh my God, give five babies as this one ...

The boy looked at the bride with a quarrelsome look, that is, the bride shouldn't play with her children near her father-in-law, both her parents and the bride understood it.

- Oh no, let it be her only shame, - said his mother, taking the child from the bride, she began to recite:

- Give such baby to the flying birds,

Give such baby to the unmarried girls...” (3, p. 322-323)

Here, in addition to the love of mother-child or grandmother-grandson the beauty of the sincere relationship among the bride and family members, especially family adults, also complements the mood created by the poetic text. Movlud Suleymanli demonstrated such a deep and close attachment to folklore, especially folklore symbolism, both at the level of the image and the descent of individual motives in the narrative “Mill” that the work is a translation of the national spirit for its linguistic and stylistic qualities, its original color indicators, as well as for its artistic and aesthetic character as a whole (5, p.93).

The images such as Shepherd Shamil in the novel “Saltness” or Dede in the work “Migration” or the character grandmother Huru appear in the certain episodes of the plot line, the historical-spiritual values, national-mental qualities reflected in their faces - outlook, behavior and thoughts - become the main essence expressing the main essence of those works.

The image Shepherd Shamil in the novel “Saltness” takes the events in front of a man’s eyes in the light of the historical experience of yesterday and the past and comes to the conclusion that they do not have any meaning - they are “desalted”. Feeling anxious about the danger of this “desalination” taking the country and people out of the stream of their ancestors and directing them in a dark and vain direction, the wise man wants to connect young shepherds to their native land with his admonishing conversations and far-sighted advice.

For Shamil the sense of dignity, self-pride, folk self-esteem are the main ones. According to his conclusion, these values stand at the forefront of all kinds of materialism. The elder Shepherd, who often expresses with his admonitions almost every day that light, external radiance, false, wrong actions inflict lethal blows on human spirituality, sees the solution to the problem in attachment to the path of ancestors, that is, in self-realization.

Movlud Suleymanli shows the mission of not breaking the historical-spiritual connection and carrying it from yesterday to today with the essence of the epics spoken by Agh Ozan and Goycha Ozan: “Ozan Goycha came from the country Goshgarç but Agh Ozan came from the tribe Garakelleler. They played and sang about their observation, past and future”.

The inclusion of symbolic images from folklore in the network of artistic characters, the generalization of many events in the plot in the symbolic plan with a special purpose, the meaning of multi-faceted episodes with the possibility of interpreting them in the most different directions from the plane of history and modernity deepens the artistic nature and content of the work. From the memory of the epic the characters such as Dede, Beyrek, Agh Ozan, Chickek, Domrul, Bekil,

including the symbolization of events in accordance with the author’s idea gives the novel great power in the sense of nationality.

In the artistic portrait of the characters bearing the names from the novel “Dede Gorgud” the character, manner of action and behavior, feelings and thoughts of the predecessors are also reflected to the considerable extent. For example, the portrait lines of Domrul in the novel “Migration”, similar to his predecessor in the epic, Deli Domrul, can serve as a vivid example of it: “Many donkeys could not pull the cart held by Domrul. He used to break the thick bone of the animal with his hand. He used to hold the millstone in the mill, holding the horse on his shoulder and leading it ten paces. In this way, Deli Domrul would entertain the people and the people would feed him. He would eat thirty eggs and drink a big jug of sour milk during the dinner time. The old men used to say that there were many such men in Garakelleler, but they were not crazy”.

It is possible to see alike similarities in the portraits of other characters. The character of Dede, the elder person in the novel “Migration”, also has spiritual and historical qualities that echo and intersect directly with the world of Dede Gorgud, including Dede Gorgud himself. Dede is the head of the tribe, the symbol of the respected tribal hearth, the protector and the guide. He is the spiritual power that carries the unique knowledge and life experience of the clan-tribe’s yesterday – the historical memory to today. Tomorrow’s direction depends on his wise advice and recommendations: “An old man with a white beard was sitting comfortably on the back of a white camel, as if he was sitting on the ground”.

Ilyas Efendiyev was one of the writers who had made great creative contributions to Azerbaijani prose and had a rich legacy of vivid, fresh images and artistic means of description. Ilyas Efendiyev is leading scientific thinker. A whole generation of actors and directors were trained in the performances based on his 15 plays (such as “You are always with me”, “Destroyed diaries”, “The song remained in the mountains”, “In the crystal palace”, “Khurshidbanu Natavan”), which he gave to our literature and stage and the “Ilyas Efendiyev Theater” was established. Ilyas Efendiyev’s activity is clear and his deep philosophy is nourished by the folk spirituality. Because his activity has developed in the background of folk life and has found its way.

It is undeniable that the national and moral values of our people play an exceptional role in the education of the younger generation in the writer’s works. These works are of exceptional importance in the development of literature, both in artistic terms and due to the load of meaning testifies to the richness of the writer’s soul. The fact that he is an artist who always lives among the people and that he chooses heroes from among the people for his works is proof that he is a great patriot. The color of the mysterious speech labels in the language of the images proves once again that the writer is an

irreplaceable artist who is connected to the people, close to the people's spirit and deeply familiar with it. The characteristics of Ilyas Efendiyev's activity, which is firmly connected to national identity, folklore and classical heritage, are modernity and nationalism with human content. The writer raised the language and artistic style to the level of a new literary school in our literature. The language of the writer's artistic works is very rich with stylistic nuances from the lexicon of legends, narratives, fairy tales and epics. The language of our people is its priceless wealth.

In several historical dramas such as "The song remained in the mountains", "Khurshidbanu Natavan", "Sheikh Mahammad Khiyabani", "Lovers' joining in the hell", "Lonely oleaster tree", "The wise and the mad", "The ruler and his daughter" the struggle for the freedom and independence of our people is presented in the language of images with unique shades. These heroes are true devotees who fought for the freedom and independence of the people.

From the play "Khurshidbanu Natavan": Natavan: "If there is a truth in this world called happiness, then it lies only in the fact that a person has his own homeland and own self. I believe in the power of freedom. True freedom of conscience is necessary for the flourishing of beautiful feelings and beautiful thoughts of a person, for the rise of human dignity". These words are the leitmotif of the drama "Khurshidbanu Natavan". The unity, freedom, culture, language and national independence of Azerbaijan are the main goals for the poetess, public figure Natavan (6, p. 7).

The play "Khurshidbanu Natavan" is dedicated to the famous poetess Khurshidbanu Natavan, the daughter of the Karabakh Khan Mehdigulu Khan. The main character of the work is Khurshidbanu Natavan. For the first time, the reader gets acquainted with the character of Natavan in Tbilisi, in the Caucasian viceroyalty, witnesses her conversation with the Viceroy, sees the behavior and dignity of this zealous and bigoted girl representing the Azerbaijani people, feels pride.

The Viceroy accepts the young poetess with respect and attention worthy of the Khan's daughter. On the one hand, Natavan's erudition, decisive and beautiful speech, spiritual richness surprise the Viceroy and on the other hand force him to treat this young girl with respect and courtesy. The writer wants to say with this episode that no one will appreciate the one who does not appreciate himself. This is exactly how a representative of the people should behave. Natavan's behavior with the representative of the Empire is a manifestation of the determination and dignity of the Azerbaijani people.

The beginning of Natavan's first love appeared in that meeting. Although the mutual marriage with the young prince Khasay, who was a nobleman from

Dagestan, was short-lived, it showed Natavan's character integrity, philanthropy and humanity. When Khasay was helpless before his uncle's request to return to Dagestan, Natavan advised him to leave, no matter how difficult the separation was and justified the separation: "I will not tolerate you being subjected to the curses of your fellow countrymen!".

Natavan is looking for ways to improve the situation of the people and is trying to do everything possible. She always thinks about the fate of certain people of South Azerbaijan under the servitude of the royal system of Iran. The main feature characterizing Natavan in the play is her unity with the people, her ideas and thoughts about the people. Her deep feelings of love for her native land, for the working people who are the real owners of this land, are not confined only to the borders of Karabakh.

Khurshidbanu Natavan is also a talented poetess with the ability to skillfully glorify subtle human feelings. The words by the Caucasian Viceroy "I heard that you are also a wonderful poetess" give information about the poetic glory of the Khan's daughter.

Though the play "Khurshidbanu Natavan" is written on a historical theme, it is a very valuable work that resonates with our modern life. Therefore, the play was accepted well and highly appreciated by readers and viewers.

Thus, the coloring speech etiquette in the language of images has a wide dioposon, which is difficult to summarize in one article. The speech labels among the members of the society of each nation are part of the general culture of that nation. Speech labels of images in fiction are specific speech norms of the people, the nation. For this reason, modernity is fundamental in cultural language labels. This modernity must be constantly reflected from fiction. This modernity should always be reflected in fiction.

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